

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/365604632>

A Case of Neonatal Scabies Infection

Article · July 2022

CITATIONS

0

READS

609

4 authors:

Aishwarya Bajpai

Hind institute of medical sciences Safedabaad

6 PUBLICATIONS 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Ekansh Rathoria

UNS AUTONOMOUS STATE MEDICAL COLLEGE JAUNPUR UTTAR PRADESH- 222001

27 PUBLICATIONS 17 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Utkarsh Bansal

Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Barabanki, India

49 PUBLICATIONS 97 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Divya Sachdeva

Hind institute of medical sciences, Safedabad

1 PUBLICATION 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

Study of serum IgE levels in childhood asthma in Barabanki region, India [View project](#)

Simulation [View project](#)

A Case of Neonatal Scabies Infection

Aishwarya Bajpai*, Utkarsh Bansal**, Ekansh Rathoria*, Divya Sachdeva**

*Postgraduate, Department of Pediatrics, Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Safedabad, Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh, India aishwaryabajpai92@gmail.com, **MD (Pediatrics), Professor and Head, Department of Pediatrics, Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Safedabad, Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh, India, email : utkarsh1003@gmail.com, *MD (Pediatrics), Associate Professor, Department of Pediatrics, Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Safedabad, Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh, India, email : rathoriaekansh@yahoo.com, ** Postgraduate, Department of Pediatrics, Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Safedabad, Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh, India, email: divyasachdeva521@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

Neonatal scabies is a rare entity, and due to the non-classical clinical presentation in this age group the diagnosis is often missed or delayed. Unlike the classical cases in which lesions are usually confined to flexural aspects of limbs, interdigital spaces, neonatal scabies presents with generalized lesions, with involvement of head, face, neck, palms, and soles, with a vesico-pustular character of lesions. We present case of a 3-week-old neonate with scabies involving whole family, who was successfully treated.

INTRODUCTION

Scabies is a parasitic infestation, caused by the female mite *Sarcoptes scabiei* var. *hominis*, of the skin. This highly contagious infestation is spread by direct contact with the skin of the infested person. The clothes and bedding of the infested person may also act like a source when used recently. [1]

It presents with papular lesions which are extremely itchy leading to excoriations and discomfort. Scabies is a common problem persisting in the community, specially affecting the children, as it is frequently not diagnosed correctly and even if diagnosed complete treatment requiring therapy of all the affected family members is often overlooked.

CASE HISTORY

A 3-week-old male infant presented to the pediatric outpatient department for the evaluation of a rash present all over the body. The rash was first noticed by the mother 15 days back over the abdomen but it gradually spread all over the body including the infant's face, neck, head, and extremities. The infant was irritable but was breastfeeding normally.

The baby was born full term via normal vaginal delivery. The prenatal, natal and postnatal laboratory tests of the mother and child, including TORCH infections and HIV, were negative. Systemic examination was within normal limit.

On examination the baby was alert, well nourished, and comfortable in his mother's arms. The lesions were papulopustular and vesicular present on his chest, abdomen, back, arms, legs, neck, and buttocks [Figure 1]. The pustules and vesicles had an erythematous base in different stages of development, with some containing yellowish fluid and some crusted.

The patient's mother also had lesions all over the body which were erythematous scaly involving the axilla, breast, abdomen and feet. Mother also complained of itching over the lesions. [Figure 2]

All routine investigations were normal. Blood and skin swab cultures, and syphilis RPR (rapid plasma reagent), were negative. Skin scrapings revealed scabies egg and fecal matter of mite, which confirmed the diagnosis of neonatal scabies.

The treatment regimen recommended was topical application of permethrin 5% cream below the neck region on whole body, to be kept overnight and to wash off after 8-10 hours next morning. A repeat application was advised after 1 week. All family members were also treated. The infant showed improvement, with no new lesions or worsening of previous lesions on follow up.

Figure 1: Papulopustular and vesicular lesions present on infants' chest, abdomen, back, arms, legs, neck, and buttock

Figure 2: Lesions over the patient's mother involving axilla, feet and abdomen

DISCUSSION Aetiology and pathogenesis

The female scabies mite measures 0.3×0.4 mm and has 4 pair of legs and has a lifespan of 4-6 weeks. The gravid female mite secretes a substance which dissolves the skin scales and consumes it, creating a burrow on the skin at the rate of 0.5-5 mm per day. It then lays down an average of three eggs per day, up to 50 eggs, inside the burrow which hatch within 2-3 days. The larva has three pair of legs, and it transforms through three nymph stages to reach adulthood. The copulation of male and female mites occurs within burrow in the skin. A mite can survive for 24-36 h at room temperature in the environment while the nymph forms may survive 2-5 days. [3] Their survival is longer in humid and cool environment. [4] A scabies patient may harbour 10-15 female mites at a time.

About one month after the initial infestation, the symptoms of clinical scabies appear, which are due to the hosts immune response against the mite. The specific antigens leading to the immune reaction are unknown but are postulated to be the saliva, the substance that dissolves keratin, the scybala (faecal matter) or the mite itself. The lesions are intensely pruritic leading to scratching which may injure the mites and limit the spread of the infestation. The immune response itself is incapable of eliminating the disease or preventing re-infestation. In cases of scabies re-infestation the symptoms appear quickly, within 24 – 48 hours, and the associated pruritis and itching may prevent the infestation from becoming re-established, due to the heightened immune response which gradually wanes off. [3,5]

The immunocompromised or neurologically disabled patients, can host a significantly high number of mites with minimal symptoms of pruritis, leading to crusted (Norwegian) scabies. [3]

Transmission

Transmission in the paediatric population mainly occurs via prolonged contact with infected children or caregivers. Mites take about 15–20 minutes to transfer between people. Transmission by fomites is rare as the survival of the mite is 2-3 days only in the environment. [6,7]

Clinical Features

The most common presentation of scabies is itching over lesions. The worsening of itching in the night which is usually typical but not specific is termed as nocturnal crescendo. [8]

The lesions appear like dermatitis due to repeated scratching which excoriation and crusting of the lesions. [9]

Lesions tend to have a typical distribution involving axilla, flexural aspect of elbows, dorsal aspect of ankle, the interdigital web spaces of hand and feet, ano-genital region and truncal areas, particularly the nipples and periumbilical region. This is peculiar distribution is termed as the circle of Hebra. [10]

Infants and toddlers usually are the most suffered family members with extensive lesions involving the palms and soles, scalp and face because of their inability to scratch and restrict the infestation unlike adults, leading to the infantile scabies. [11] Scabies nodules are more commonly seen in infants and toddlers. Vesico-pustular lesions on palms and soles are the hallmark of infantile scabies.

Management [3,12,13,14]

- Successful treatment of scabies requires not only the treatment of symptoms but elimination of the mites; and treatment of secondary infection if present.
- All the used clothes, bed covers, and towels should be washed in hot water and sun-dried. Toys, and other items that cannot be washed may be stored in bags for a week, as the mite will die within this period.
- The scabidical agent should be applied all over the body below the neck, whether involved or uninvolved, including on nail beds, genital region, soles of feet, etc.
- If itching persists for >2 weeks after treatment or new lesions appear, the patient should be examined for re-infection.
- The treatment should be provided to all the family members and caregivers of the infested child.
- Nodules are treatment-resistant and require prolonged treatment for months.
- In infants and children <2 years lesions are found above the neck necessitating treatment of the scalp as well.
- Anti-histaminic (fexofenadine, hydroxyzine, cetirizine) are given for 1- 2 weeks to reduce pruritis. Not recommended in infants <6 months.
- Antibiotics can be given if there is evidence of secondary bacterial infection.
- Patient should be reviewed after a week

Table 1: Antiscabietic drugs Scabicide	Route	Dosing Schedule	Repeat Dose	Age Group
5% Permethrin cream	Local application	Apply from neck down; wash off after 8-14 hr	After 2 week	Infants >2 months, most commonly used agent
1% Lindane lotion or cream	Local Application	Apply 30-60 mL from neck down; wash off after 8-12 hr	After 1 week	Infants >6 months
10% Crotamiton cream or lotion	Local application	Two applications daily for 14 days	Daily for 14 days	Infants <2 months
2-10% Sulphur in petrolatum ointments	Local application	Apply for 24 hours	Repeat for 3 consecutive days	Infants >2 months. 6% preferred
10-25% Benzoyl benzoate lotion	Local application	Apply for 24 hours	After 24 hours	>2 years, 12.5% in young children
0.5% Malathion lotion	Local application	Apply for 24 hours	After 7 days	Infants >6months
1% Malathion shampoo	Local application	For scalp application	After 7 days	Infants >6months
Ivermectin	Oral	200ug/kg single dose	14 days	>5 years, >15 kg

DECLARATIONS

Ethical approval: Approval taken by the Institute Ethics Committee.

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR:**Dr Utkarsh Bansal**

Professor & Head, Department of Pediatrics,
Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Safedabad, Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh, India
email : utkarsh1003@gmail.com

FINANCIAL SUPPORT & SPONSORSHIP

NIL

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DISCLOSURE

There is no conflict of interest to be declared by the authors.

REFERENCES

1. **Walker JGA, Johnstone PW.** Interventions for treating scabies. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev* 2000;(3):CD000320.
2. **Johnston G, Sladden M.** Scabies: diagnosis and treatment. *BMJ* 2005;331:619–22
3. **Julie S. Prendiville.** Scabies and Lice. In: Irvine A, Hoeger P, Yan A., editors. *Harper's Textbook of Pediatric Dermatology*. Wiley Blackwell. Volume 1. 3rd Edition 2011, p. 72.1-72.8
4. **Liu JM, Wang HW, Chang FW, et al.** The effects of climate factors on scabies A 14-year population-based study in Taiwan. *Parasite*. 2016;23
5. **Cabrera R, Agar A, Dahl MV.** The immunology of scabies. *Semin Dermatol*. 1993;12:15 – 21
6. **Kazeminejad A, Hajheydari Z, Ghahari MJ.** Scabies treatment in children: a narrative review. *JPR*. 2019;7(2):105–112.
7. **Thomas C, Coates S, Engleman D, et al.** Ectoparasites: scabies. *J Am Acad Dermatol*. 2020;82(3):533–548.
8. **Lavery MJ, Stull C, Nattkemper LA, et al.** Nocturnal pruritus: prevalence, characteristics, and impact on ItchyQoL in a chronic itch population. *Acta Derm Venereol*. 2017;97:513–515.
9. **Thomas C, Coates SJ, Engelman D, et al.** Ectoparasites: scabies. *J Am Acad Dermatol*. 2020;82:533–548
10. **Walton SF, Currie BJ.** Problems in diagnosing scabies, a global disease in human and animal populations. *Clin Microbiol Rev*. 2007;20(2):268–279.
11. **Boralevi F, Diallo A, Miquel J, et al.** Clinical phenotype of scabies by age. *Pediatrics*. 2014;133:e910–e916.
12. **Daren A. Diiorio, Stephen R. Humphrey.** Scabies. In : **Kliegman Robert M, Geme Joseph W, Blum Nathan J, Tasker Rober C, Shah Samir S, Wilson Karen M, Behrman Richard E.**, editors. *Nelson Textbook of Pediatrics*. 21st Edition. Philadelphia: Elsevier, 2020. p. 3570-74
13. **Khanna N., Bhari N.** Skin Disorders. Diseases caused by arthropods. In: **Paul Vinod K, Bagga A**, editors. *Ghai Essential Pediatrics*. CBS Publishers and distributors. 9th ed 2019 p. 699-700
14. **Vasanwala FF, Ong CY, Aw CWD, How CH.** Management of scabies. *Singapore Med J*. 2019 Jun;60(6):281-285.